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Subtype selection in TNBC is conducted by the LSD1-associated *Phf2011* and the Xist RNP.

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TNBC is a product of selection pressure in a transformed cell of origin that generates hormone receptor-positive and hormone receptor-negative breast cancer types. We recently discovered activation of Xist in p53-deficient breast cancer, existence of an Xist RNP that conducts gene regulation in normal conditions in somatic cells and evidence for existence of multiple variant Xist RNP complexes that conduct similar but unique gene regulation programs in transformation and human cancer. We recently demonstrated existence of an Xist RNP complex containing Matr3 and function of the Matr3-containing Xist RNP in selection of the luminal A subtype in human breast cancer. We demonstrate here composition of an Xist RNP complex containing the LSD1-associated demethylase Phf2011 during subtype selection of androgen receptor (AR) positive (AR+) and AR- TNBC cancer types. Xist functions as a stimulus or associated product of selection pressure that drives cellular evolution. In both hormone receptor positive (luminal A) and in hormone receptor negative (AR- and AR+ TNBC), discrete Xist RNP complexes with unique complex composition function through driving selection pressure molecule subtype selection.